

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LONO-BATURA****FIRST NAME: MAILE****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 17%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Mac OS 14.4.1

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. James Sampson states that, ‘a well-developed _____ is the foundation for valid research.’

- Research question¹**
- Qualitative approach
- Literature review
- Quantitative approach

2. Dr. Phillip Adu notes in his video, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*, that being _____ increases the credibility of the study.

¹James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Creative Commons Attribution, 2017), 17.

Transparent²

Professional

Candid

A professor

3. Bloomberg and Volpe discuss the role limitations and delimitations have in the research process, stating that ‘Qualitative limitations are threats to transferability, _____, confirmability, and _____.’ Select two:

Dependability³

Credibility

Reproducibility

Accountability

²*Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. Methodology Related Presentations – TCSPP. Phillip Adu (YouTube, March 6, 2016), 1:05:16 min., <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

³Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 437-438.

4. What is the purpose of delimitations?

Clarify what will not be examined⁴

Demonstrate rigor

Serve as a quality checkpoint

Provide a study road map

5. Sampson underscores the importance of transparency in stating that, ‘Evidence of transparency is demonstrated by the doctoral student’s ability to describe their _____ about the content and process of measurement, as stated in the measures section of the dissertation.’

Perceptions⁵

Realizations

Adaptations

Conclusions

⁴Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 49.

⁵Ibid., 42.

6. According to Bloomberg & Volpe, ‘Indigenous methodologies value experiential and personal stories, including those of the researcher. This research approach is not only concerned with knowledge creation and cocreation but it is also about healing and _____ - _____.’

Community-building⁶

Story-telling

Best-practices

Community-engagement

7. In Turabian Rule of Style, sources are discussed in a tiered model that includes primary, secondary, and tertiary sources. These varied sources allow you to ‘engage not just its words and ideas, but also its implications, consequences, _____, and new possibilities.’

Shortcomings⁷

Highlights

Cases

Findings

⁶Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 185.

⁷Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 121.

8. By creating a dissertation, you are NOT _____ the body of evidence that explores your selected topic.

Discounting⁸

Evaluating

Building

Evolving

9. Kate L. Turabian went into detail around the critical elements and necessary style requirements for a dissertation. A successful dissertation is one that presents its ideas clearly. Turabian notes that 'Readers understand a sentence most readily when they grasp its subject easily, and the easiest subject to grasp is not just short and concrete but also _____.'

Familiar⁹

Academic

Researched

Simple

⁸Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed., 22.

⁹Ibid., 121.

10. What is NOT necessary for Institutional Review Board Approval?

- Annotated bibliography**¹⁰
- Research proposal
- Overview of methodology
- Qualitative and quantitative research timeline

¹⁰Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 202-203.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube. March 6, 2016. 1:05:16 min. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&t=6s>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.